

Institutional Energy Management System: A Path towards Sustainability for Multicultural Educational Institutions

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ABSTRACT: Electrical energy demand has been rapidly increasing over the past few years. This results in widening the gap between demand and supply of energy in developed and under developed countries. To overcome this issue load shedding has been deployed which has promoted the use of backup power solutions which also increases burden on the energy sector. Therefore, to optimize the energy utilization, energy audits have been introduced to save energy consumption. This paper summarizes the energy conservation measures adopted in various allied multicultural educational institutes i.e., Academic buildings of University of Engineering and Technology Lahore (RCET Campus), Boarding Houses, Residential Blocks, Agricultural Unit, Students Club, Mess Block etc. to make sure economical electricity consumption and to identify the reasons that are causing excessive use of energy. The initial data was collected by survey forms that were used further to determine types of electricity loads, pattern of energy consumption, energy wastages points, and common habits of people regarding electricity use. During walk through audit, lighting section of the building was noticed to be one of the major causes of electricity wastage. In detailed energy audit, the appliances ratings were measured and compared with their pre-defined efficiency. Moreover, it provides 53.84% reduction in replacing and by removing surplus lighting load, a 47.7% reduction in replacing and removing surplus fan load, while 46.6% and 72.8% reduction in air conditioning load and informational systems respectively. These efforts resulted in an overall savings of 55.23%, ensuing in a significant reduction of United States Dollar (USD) 12770 in electricity costs.

The research provided in this paper can help educational facilities improve their energy management practices, which will lead to a more environmentally friendly and sustainable future.

Keywords: Energy Management, Energy conservation measures, Energy consumption, Energy efficiency

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1. Introduction

Energy demand in developed and under developed countries is increasing day by day. The major reason is that people are switching their life styles. The same thing is happening in the educational institutes also. They are dealing with a number of energy management issues as they transition to more modern systems, which cost them in terms of monthly electricity bills. So, there is a need of a methodology by implementing which it is possible to achieve the balance between demand and supply of the energy. Therefore, Energy Audit is one of the methodologies which could be apply to get the desired results.

Energy Audit is a process in which energy consumption is reduced to save electricity, improve the efficiency and to make the system more economical by restricting the causes of the losses to the maximum possible level. The implementation of the energy audit is of three types:(Kals 2015, Kontokosta, Spiegel-Feld et al. 2020)

1. Walk-through Energy Audit
2. Detail Energy Audit
3. Target Energy Audit

This research paper summarizes the findings of the energy audit conducted to thoroughly examine the energy usage of academic buildings with the purpose of identifying areas for improvement and implementing strategies to improve energy efficiency. A question-based study was conducted to identify personal opinions and habits of the students and employees regarding their energy consumption patterns. The recommendations are provided to replace the inefficient appliances with the efficient ones along with their payback periods. The findings of energy audit, the measures implemented to reduce energy consumption, and the resulting energy savings are presented in this paper. The goal of this study is to represent the importance of energy audits and show the potential for significant energy savings in educational institute buildings.

Energy audits are becoming increasingly important in a variety of industries, including educational institutions and residential hostels. These audits enable organizations to gain valuable insights into their energy consumption patterns and help identify opportunities for reducing energy usage.

(Adewale, Adekitan et al. 2018), presents a case study discussed which concluded that a building load is dependent on three different combinations of sources i.e., Smart Grid, Solar PV and Diesel Generator. The most efficient and highly yielded combinations are Grid (100%) > Grid (75%) & Solar PV system (25%) > Grid (50%) & Diesel (50%). In another case, energy was saved by replacing incandescent bulbs with LED bulbs as incandescent bulbs are not well for the environment due to presence of mercury and its life cycle is also shorter.

According to the ECBC (Energy Conservation Building Code) standard, buildings must conserve a minimum of 25% on energy, 35% for ECBC Plus buildings, and 50% or more for Super-ECBC structures. This study concentrated on electrical appliance-related energy-saving strategies. The tested building met ECBC requirements because of energy savings of 27.4%. Inspection and execution are essential for ECBC to be effective, and additional energy can be saved by making structural changes and relying more on natural lighting. The market trend indicates a greater use of ECBC standards in new projects and the energy efficiency modification of older structures(Sendrayaperumal, Mahapatra et al. 2021).

For the sake of awareness about energy waste and conservation, another pattern is being followed in which all types of equipment and loads are distributed in different sections such as: Lighting, HVAC, Motor & Drives, Processes and Other Electrical Equipment. Each section consists of a checklist having different type of questions in it to test the reliability. After answering all the questions, it is possible to clearly diagnose the current status of equipment or load whether it is in good condition or it is about to get any fault nearly or it should be replaced now etc.(King and Perry 2017).

In order to cut costs, a case study at KNUST (Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology) in Ghana studied solar energy and sustainable energy conservation measures. Renovation of cooling systems, illumination and ventilation systems could result in per month energy savings of 163,400 kWh, or 5% of total energy. This appears into a potential monthly cost savings of USD 37,880. According to a financial evaluation, involving large-scale solar PV could result in 20-year savings of USD 69.1 million with a 6-year payback period. These results highlight the significance of adopting renewable energy sources and energy-efficient practices in public higher education institutions(Opoku, Adjei et al. 2020).

Gap in the Existing Research:

Existing research work related to energy management systems at the university buildings has mainly focused on technical aspects; such as diagnoses of inefficient energy consuming loads and their subsequent replacement with efficient devices, inclusion of renewable sources to reduce energy bills of the universities (Bosu, Mahmoud et al. 2023, Zagrajek, Kłos et al. 2023). The impact of building users/occupants on energy consumption need to be considered, energy conservation through design optimization need to be focused. Moreover there is a need to incorporate United Nations Sustainable development goals in such studies at the university premises.

Addressing the Gap

This study is to address a major knowledge gap in the area of educational institutes energy audits. The impact of faculty and students' demographics, perceptions, and daily habits on energy wastage will be considered. Moreover emphases will be placed on the actual need of a specific load; that is surplus loads will be identified and removed, energy efficiency measures have been intelligently suggested, re-location of some large cooling loads have been worked instead of sticking with existing locations of the loads. Promising results in reducing energy consumption in university buildings have also been achieved through the use of HAP software for designing energy efficient air conditioning load (Akkoyunlu and Banaez 2024). This research intends to make significant progress in the effort to minimize energy waste in buildings by filling in these gaps. In addition, it promotes sustainable development by suggesting energy-saving measures to cut down on the general use of energy.

Article Organization

The study is categorized as an introduction is provided in Section I, and the energy audit methodology is described in Section II. The energy audit performed on the campus building is discussed in detail in Section III, which covers a wide range of topics, including correlations and results, energy-efficient strategies regarding lighting and fan loads, the installation of an energy-efficient cooling system for the computer lab, energy-saving measures for the informational system, and energy-efficient approaches regarding air conditioning. The opportunity for conserving energy through eliminating the surplus loads is also highlighted. The study is then summed up and drawn to a conclusion in Sections IV and V.

2. Methodology

For the sake of data collection, a Google survey form was designed and information was collected by visiting each office and classroom of the academic building. In the very first step, information was collected by using survey form in order to get to know about the energy consumption pattern in university building. After conducting the survey, daily consumption of various loads was observed and measured.

Figure 1: Methodology Framework

Furthermore, it was suggested to replace the inefficient loads with the efficient ones and their payback period was also calculated. In the end, a recommendation report was made in which all possible factors are mentioned which are causing energy wastage in the building as well as their solutions is also provided by following which energy consumption and electricity billing cost could be reduced.

3. Energy Audit at University's Academic Building

Questionnaire Survey and its findings

A total of 409 respondents actively engaged in the Google survey, approximately 20% of them were females, 10% of the respondents speak Pashto as their native language and belong to KPK province of Pakistan, 90% of the respondents belong to Punjab province of Pakistan out of these 60% speak Punjabi as mother tongue, while 30% speak Saraiki as native language; thus the respondents belong to different geographical, ethnic and cultural groups. The survey was intentionally designed with two key elements. Firstly, participants rated electrical equipment. Secondly, students and teachers reported their typical campus building usage durations. By including inquiries about energy-saving habits, like turning off appliances when leaving spaces, we discerned energy consumption patterns using this approach. Minitab helps researchers find patterns and relationships between different variables through the use of correlation calculations and graphical representations of the data (Kenett and Zacks 2021, Okagbue, Oguntunde et al. 2021).

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{(\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2)(\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2)}} \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) could also be used to find out the correlation values. These values are used to determine the logical pattern of a relationship between two variables. Correlation can take on values between -1 and 1, where -1 indicates an exactly opposite connection (perfect negative correlation) and 1 indicates a perfectly direct relationship (Ullah, Garg et al. 2020).

TABLE I: Correlation among the Habits of University's Faculty

Correlation among the habits of University's Faculty		
Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation
Habit to turn off appliances before leaving the office	Habit to properly shutdown the laptop	0.912
	Habit to utilize sunlight	0.426
	Have opinion that university is not getting free of cost electricity	0.535
Habit to properly shutdown the laptop	Habit to utilize sunlight	0.960
	Have opinion that individual wastes electricity effects.	0.597
	Habit to turn off appliances at home	0.815
Habit to utilize sunlight	Habit to turn off corridors' lights	0.618
	Have opinion that university is not getting free of cost electricity	0.713
	Waste energy because they are not answerable	0.546
	Have opinion that excess power consumption effects environment	0.975
Habit to turn off corridors' lights	Have opinion that university is not getting free of cost electricity	0.969
	Have opinion that excess power consumption effects environment	0.704
Have opinion that university is not getting free of cost electricity	Waste energy because they are not answerable	0.811

The Table I represents that there is a strong correlation (0.912) between the persons who have habit to turn off appliances before leaving the office and habit to properly shutdown the laptops and there are very weak relationships between the individuals who have habit to turn off appliances before leaving the office and habit to turn off the corridors' lights. The faculty members have been observed to switch off their appliances before leaving, however, they do not seem to follow the same practice when it comes to turning off the lights in the corridors. In the same a very strong correlation (0.975) is found between the members who have habit to utilize sunlight and who have opinion that excess power consumption results in negative impacts on the environment. Another strong correlation (0.969) is observed between the persons who have habit to turn off corridors' lights and who have opinion that university is not getting free of cost electricity.

TABLE II: Correlation among the Habits of University Students

Correlation among the habits of University Students		
Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation
Habit to use sunlight	Noticed energy saving initiatives in the university	0.827
	Get the awareness on energy conservation from university	0.573
Habit to properly shutdown the laptop	Habit to use sunlight	0.681
	Have knowledge about energy audit	0.722
Avoid to charge laptops/mobiles in class	Habit to turn off appliances before leaving the class	0.627
	Habit to turn off corridors' lights	0.853
	Noticed energy saving initiatives in the university	0.506
Have knowledge about energy audit	Habit to use sunlight	0.547
	Habit to shut down the laptop	0.722

In Table II it is described that the students who notice energy saving initiatives also have habit to use sunlight (0.827). Another strong correlation exists between the students who have knowledge about energy audit they also have habit to properly shutdown their laptops (0.722). In another case it is mentioned that the students who have habit to turn off corridors lights in day time also have habit to avoid charge their laptops/mobile phones in classrooms.

Correlation between two things is found in order to see how one thing is linked to another. For example, some members think that the government gives free electricity, so we should waste energy because we are not accountable. Conversely, some members who are aware of energy audits use sunlight and turn off appliances before leaving the room.

Existing Load Details of University’s Academic Building

The total load of the academic building mainly consists of lighting load, cooling load, electric geysers and electronic information systems.

Figure 2: Annual energy consumption of various loads

The lighting load includes Incandescent bulbs, CFLs, Fluorescent tube and LED bulbs. While the cooling load consist of ceiling fans and air conditioners. On the other hand, Computers, Printers and WIFI devices represents the electronic information system load.

Lighting Load:

The inefficient lighting sources consist of incandescent bulbs, fluorescent tubes, and compact fluorescent lamps. LED bulbs and tubes have been included in the category of load, but their proportion is very low. The operational hours are 1560 in a year.

Figure 3 lists all types of lighting loads that are currently in use on campus, including LEDs, Incandescent Lamps, CFLs, and Fluorescent Tubes, in addition to their percentage usage.

Figure 3: Types of Lighting Load

Suggested Replacements of the inefficient lighting load

The existing inefficient lighting loads such as CFLs, fluorescent tubes and incandescent tubes could be replaced by energy efficient LED tubes and bulbs. Table III mentions the inefficient lighting load in the campus building and represents the replacement along with the investment and payback period.

$$EC \left(\frac{kWh}{year} \right) = Rating(W) \times \frac{hour}{year} \times Quantity \quad (2)$$

$$ECC(USD) = EC \left(\frac{kWh}{year} \right) \times PoU \quad (3)$$

The energy consumption and it's cost for incandescent bulbs, CFLs and fluorescent tubes are 561kWh/year, 9548kWh/year, 35696kWh/year and USD 91.443, USD 1556.324, USD 5818.448 respectively, which are calculated by using (2) and (3), where 1unit= 1kWh costsUSD0.163.The discount rate defined for Pakistan is 17%(Akbar 2023).

$$ES \left(\frac{kWh}{year} \right) = EC_{Existing} \left(\frac{kWh}{year} \right) - EC_{New} \left(\frac{kWh}{year} \right) \quad (4) \quad ESC(USD) = ES \left(\frac{kWh}{year} \right) \times PoU(USD) \quad (5)$$

Equation (6) is used to calculate the payback period by using initial investment, discount rate and cost saving(Maghsoudi and Sadeghi 2020, Hu, Huang et al. 2023).

$$PP(Days) = \frac{-\ln\left(1 - \frac{(ININ \times DR)}{ESC}\right)}{\ln(1+DR)} \quad (6)$$

The initial investment, energy savings and energy cost savings for replacing incandescent bulbs, CFLs and fluorescent tubes are USD 213.61, USD 31.41, USD 1174.52, 9547kWh/year, 4119 kWh/year, 27297 kWh/year and USD 671.397, USD 1556.161, USD 4449.411 respectively, find out by utilizing (4) and (5). Equation (6) is used to calculate the payback period.

Table III: Inefficient Lighting Load

Lighting Load			
Name of Appliances	CFL	Incandescent Bulb	Fluorescent Tube
Quantity	204	30	673
Rating(W)	60	100	60
Annual Energy Consumption (kWh/yr.)	19095	4680	62993
Implementation	LED Bulb	LED Bulb	LED Tube
Rating(W)	30	12	34
Potential Energy Savings (kWh/yr.)	9547	4119	27297
Payback Period (Days)	50	14	73

Figure 4: Energy Consumption Difference with respect to Efficient and Inefficient Lighting Load

Fans

The majority of existing fans are aged fifteen to twenty years old, contributing to significant energy waste. The investigation revealed that their motors excessively heat due to their frail state, multiple re-windings, and worn-out bearings, all of which reduce their efficiency and cause them to waste energy.

The annual energy consumption of existing fan load is 40435 kWh per year while electricity consumption cost (ECC) is of USD 6590.9 which are calculated by (2) and (3). The operational hours are 1080 per year.

Suggested Replacements of the inefficient cooling load

Inefficient old fan load could be upgraded by switching to modern, energy-efficient models. The salvage price and price for a new efficient fan is USD 8.52 and USD 24.39 respectively, while the net initial investment is USD 4960.

Table IV: Existing Fan Load and their Replacement

Cooling Load	
Name of Appliances	Fan
Quantity	312
Rating(W)	120
Annual Energy Consumption(kWh/yr.)	40435
Suggested Energy Efficient Fans	
Rating(W)	75
Potential Energy Savings (kWh/yr.)	15163
Payback Period (Year)	2.658

Table IV shows that annual energy savings of 15163 kWh and energy saving cost of USD2471 would be possible as calculated by (4) and (5). On the other hand, (6) is used to calculate the payback period.

Figure 5: Energy Consumption Difference with respect to Efficient and Inefficient Fan Load

Cooling System for Computer Lab

It was required to design cooling system for the computer lab as CPU were damaging due to overheating.

Table V: Information about Computer Lab

Parameters	Values
Total Area	600 ft sq.
Roof Height	12 ft
No. of windows	03
Size of each window	36 ft sq.

For this purpose, HAP (Hourly Analysis Program) 4.90 software is used. Designing a cooling system with HAP normally involves entering building data such as size, orientation,

and location (Shira, Dorri et al. 2020, Saragasan 2021). The software then analyses the data and calculates the cooling load for the space. The user can then select and size the appropriate HVAC equipment and components, such as chillers, air handlers, and ductwork, and configure the system to meet the required cooling load while minimizing energy consumption. HAP also includes tools for evaluating system performance and optimizing controls for maximum efficiency and comfort.

Table VI: Hap 4.90 Software required input data

Parameters	Values
Region	Middle East
Location	Pakistan
City	Gujranwala
Latitude	32.2°
Longitude	72.2°
Elevation	757.9 ft
Designed cooling load operational months	March - June

Tables V and VI provide the information about computer lab and other relevant data required for simulation in HAP 4.90. To design an economical cooling system for the computer lab, two possible solutions could be considered.

Solution one

The first solution is to design a temperature control system for the lab on the first floor, which will require a 4-ton air conditioner (5.7kW) due to direct sunlight on the roof and heat from the windows. The operational hours are 450 per year and the annual energy consumption for the respective load is 2565 kWh, calculated by using (2).

Solution two

The second solution is to shift the lab to the ground floor because there is no direct sunlight on the roof and sunlight cannot enter from any side that's why air conditioner of 2.5 ton (2.5kW) would be sufficient. Figure 6 shows the results captured from the HAP 4.90 software simulation. The operating hours are same as before while the annual energy consumption is reduced to 1125kWh, find out by using (2). As second solution is cost beneficial, the computer lab has been shifted to ground floor. Table VII shows the required cooling load and energy consumption calculated using HAP 4.90 for both of the options available.

Figure 6: Air Conditioning System sizing for Computer Lab (Solution two)

Air System Sizing Summary for CS-Lab System		
Project Name: Computer Lab Prepared by: RCET		01/24/2023 05:00PM
Air System Information		
Air System Name.....	CS-Lab System	Number of zones.....
Equipment Class.....	PKG VERT	Floor Area.....
Air System Type.....	VAV	Location.....
		Pakistan
Sizing Calculation Information		
Calculation Months.....	Apr to Sep	Zone CFM Sizing.....
Sizing Data.....	Calculated	Space CFM Sizing.....
		Peak zone sensible load Individual peak space loads
Central Cooling Coil Sizing Data		
Total coil load.....	2.8 Tons	Load occurs at.....
Total coil load.....	36.0 MBH	Jun 1600
Sensible coil load.....	25.8 MBH	OA DB / WB.....
Coil CFM at Jun 1600.....	642 CFM	94.6 / 79.6 °F
Max block CFM at Sep 1400.....	677 CFM	Entering DB / WB.....
Sum of peak zone CFM.....	677 CFM	78.4 / 65.6 °F
Sensible heat ratio.....	0.505 ft ² /Ton	Leaving DB / WB.....
.....	117.7	55.0 / 54.3 °F
BTU/(hr-ft ²).....	102.0	Coil ADP.....
Water flow @ 10.0 °F rise.....	N/A	51.9 °F
		Bypass Factor.....
		0.100
		Resulting RH.....
		46 %
		Design supply temp.....
		55.0 °F
		Zone T-stat Check.....
		1 of 1 OK
		Max zone temperature deviation.....
		0.0 °F
Preheat Coil Sizing Data		
Max coil load.....	0.5 MBH	Load occurs at.....
Coil CFM at Des Htg.....	450 CFM	Des Htg
Max coil CFM.....	677 CFM	Ent. DB / Lvg DB.....
Water flow @ 20.0 °F drop.....	N/A	49.0 / 50.0 °F
Supply Fan Sizing Data		
Actual max CFM at Sep 1400.....	677 CFM	Fan motor BHP.....
Standard CFM.....	677 CFM	0.00 BHP
Actual max CFM/ft ²	1.35 CFM/ft ²	Fan motor kW.....
		0.00 kW
		Fan static.....
		0.00 in wg
Outdoor Ventilation Air Data		
Design airflow CFM.....	250 CFM	CFM/person.....
		15.00 CFM/person

Table VII: Designed Cooling System for Computer Lab

	At first floor	At ground floor
Required cooling load (kWh)	4 Ton	2.5 Ton
Total energy consumption (kWh)	2565 kWh/year	1125 kWh/year

The expected annual energy savings are 1440 kWh per year if the computer lab is shifted to ground floor as it is calculated with the help of (3).

Figure 7: Energy Consumption Difference with respect to Lab at First and Ground floor

The total energy consumption and total annual energy savings are calculated by using (2) and (4) respectively.

Electronic Information System

The electronic information system of the academic building consists of Computers, Printers and Wi-Fi Devices. The computers remain on idle mode for 300 hours in a year, printers stay on standby mode for 1500 hours in a year while the Wi-Fi devices operate for the 7200 hours in a year. Table VI represents the quantity, ratings, annual energy consumption calculated by (2) and energy savings as calculated by (4).

Table VIII: Existing Informational System Load

Information System Load			
Name of Appliances	Computers	Printers	Wi-Fi Devices
Quantity	150	40	70
Rating(W)	While in idle mode=80W	While in standby mode=5W	5W
Annual Energy Consumption(kWh)	3600	300	2520
Energy Saving Measures	Reduce the screen time (1/4)	By properly turning OFF	By switching OFF in off-timings (8hours)
Annual Energy savings (kWh)	2700	300	1680

In Table VIII it is described that a specific amount of energy could be saved by reducing the screen time of the computer systems by $\frac{1}{4}$ times, by properly turning off the printing machines when not in use and by switching off the Wi-Fi devices in university off timings which results in reducing the operational time by 4800 hours.

Figure 8: Energy Consumption Difference before and after the Energy Efficient Measures

Air Conditioning Load

There are number of air conditioners in the campus building and most of them are energy inefficient as they are non-inverter type. Table VII shows that air conditioning load consume 9450 kWh per year as calculated by (2).The operational hours are 630 hours per year.

Table IX: Air Conditioning Load

Air Conditioning Load	
Name of Appliances	Air conditioners (non-inverter)
Quantity	10
Rating(W)	1500
Annual Energy Consumption(kWh)	9450
Suggested Air Conditioners (Inverter)	
Rating(W)	800
Annual Energy Savings kWh	4410
Payback Period	5.68 years

Table IX suggests the replacement of the inefficient air conditioning load (non-inverters) with the efficient one (inverters) by implementing it 4410 kWh of energy could be saved annually and these savings are finding out by using (4), while payback period is calculated using (6).

Figure9: Energy Consumption Difference with respect to Efficient and Inefficient Air Conditioning Load

Energy Conservation by removing Surplus Load

During the audit, it was observed that numerous locations had an excess of lights and fans that were either unnecessary or in excess of what was needed. Removing these could result in significant energy savings. The campus corridors have the highest concentration of such loads, while there are relatively fewer in classrooms, offices, and labs throughout the university. Table X displays the expected energy savings obtained by (4) that could be achieved by removing excess loads. The operating hours for lighting and fan load are 1560 and 1080 hours per year.

Table X: Annual Energy Savings by removing unnecessary Lighting Load and Cooling Load

Annual Energy Savings by Removing Unnecessary Lighting and Fans Load		
Name of Appliances	Fluorescent Tube	Fan
Quantity	96	32
Rating(W)	60	120
Annual Energy savings(kWh)	8985.6	4147.2

Water Pump audit

A 3-phase, Δ-connected, 15HP, 4-pole motor is used for water pumping to meet campus needs. Data Collection made using eGaugeEG4xxxrevealed severe unbalancing in the line currents.

Figure 10: eGauge EG4xxx device used for measurements

It is pertinent to mention that a phase of the motor has undergone re-winding process a few years back as per the maintenance record of the motor. This certainly results in inefficient operation of the motor like; overheating of the motor and uneven mechanical stress on the motor. All the three phase windings of a three induction are required to be symmetrical. It is suggested to rewind the problematic phase in accordance with the design specifications.

4. Summary

Table XI: Expected Energy Savings in Each Area

Expected Energy Savings		
Areas of savings	Annual Energy Savings (kWh)	Annual Cost Savings
By Implementing Efficient Lighting	40963	USD 6676.96
By Implementing Efficient Fans	15163	USD 2471.569
Air Conditioning Load	4410	USD 718.83
Removing Unnecessary Lighting Load	8985	USD 1465
Removing Unnecessary Fan Load	4147	USD 675.96
By properly turning OFF printer	300	USD 50
By switching OFF in off-timings (8hours) Wi-Fi device	1680	USD 273.84
Reduce the screen time (1/4) computer	2700	USD 440.1
Total	78348	USD 12770.724

Pakistan generates electricity from coal and oil(Raza, Khatri et al. 2022). Coal and oil produce 0.00091 and 0.00078 tons of carbon dioxide emissions for every 1 kilowatt-hour of energy used(Levasseur, Mercier-Blais et al. 2021).

Table: X Expected Reduction in Carbon Footprints

Expected Reduction in Carbon Footprints	
Annual Energy Savings (kWh)	63278
Reduced Carbon Footprint (Metric Ton)	53.46

The estimated amount of energy that could be saved as a result of the recommendations is 63275 kWh, which is the product with the average carbon footprint factor (0.000845 metric tons) for coal and oil.

Carbon footprint(metric tons)=0.000845*kWh

5. Conclusion

Based on the research paper's findings, in context of multicultural educational institutions in particular, it can be said that energy audits are a useful tool for discovering energy-saving opportunities and lowering energy use in any type of building. The audit's findings revealed that making small changes—like replacing out inefficient lighting, fans and installing energy-saving HVAC systems—can result in significant energy savings.

Energy audits can facilitate educational institutions in lowering energy costs as well as lowering their carbon footprints and promoting a more sustainable future. Students' and staff's comfort and wellbeing can benefit from the adoption of energy-efficient measures.

Overall, this study highlights the necessity of performing routine energy audits and putting in place energy-efficient measures at multicultural educational institutions in particular and in any other building in general. By doing this, the organizations can help create a future that is more environmentally friendly and sustainable while also saving money on energy costs. This study also supports the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), by United Nations, which are 07, 08, 12 and 13 which states afford and clean energy, economic growth, responsible consumption and production and climate action respectively.

This paper advises that, given the favorable outcomes observed from the energy audit conducted within our multicultural institutes, it is highly recommended that other institutions follow suit. They should consider undergoing energy audits, implementing energy-efficient appliances, reducing excessive energy loads, raising awareness about the environmental repercussions of energy wastage, formulating comprehensive long-term energy efficiency policies, and forging partnerships with diverse government-affiliated energy audit firms.

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